

DESIGN, ANALYSIS AND TEST CORRELATION OF

COMPLEX COMPOSITE SHELLS OF REVOLUTION

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1-INTRODUCTION

The requirements for a combination of light weight and high strength have, for some years, pushed the aerospace industry into the structural use of composite materials and analysis of complex structural concepts. The development and use of these structures has required the parallel development of engineering analysis methods. These new methods are required to consider a variety of new problems brought about by the combinations of structural materials which were not encountered in metal analysis[1]. The composite structures are heterogeneous and nonisotropic. The failure of these structures is complicated by various, and interacting, modes. In addition the importance of the analytical tool is increased because of the non-ductile nature of the composite material failure. Thus, before new composite constituents are introduced into primary structures, the applicability of present analysis techniques to the analysis of these composite structures needs always to be demonstrated. One objective of the program reported herein was to demonstrate this analytical applicability for complicated shells of revolution encompassing graphite/epoxy sandwich construction.

2-STATE OF AUTOMATED COMPOSITE ANALYSIS

Micromechanics studies (fiber-matrix analysis models using constituent material properties) of composites often fail to agree with experimental data because of simplifications in the analysis or because the mechanical response of the constituents varies from the assumed (bulk) behavior. It is not currently feasible to perform micromechanics analysis of practical engineering

laminates and configurations. Considerable simplification is afforded by treating the composite as a laminate composed of homogeneous, anisotropic layers. Such analyses are generally referred to as macromechanics, and basic ply properties obtained from unidirectional laminates are assigned to the individual laminae. Further simplification is gained by assuming that strains are uniform or vary linearly through the thickness of the laminate at a point (Kirchoff's assumption).

Automated analysis programs for anisotropic structure analysis are currently available [2, 3]. However their ability for local analysis, such as joints, must be supplemented by special purpose composite programs [4]. In addition, their ability to predict composite sandwich buckling behavior must be tested, and may also have to be supplemented due to the many possible modes [5]. In the present design and analysis effort three computer programs are utilized, namely: STARS-2[2], ASOP[3], and PANBUCK II-R[5].

The ASOP code is a general anisotropic finite element analysis and optimization program for structures. In addition to designing metal structures for minimum weight, subject to stress and displacement constraints, there are special subroutines in the program for composites. These allow laminate optimization for weight and strength. The program has been previously applied in designing composite airplane components such as the F-14 horizontal stabilizer which was constructed from boron/epoxy [6, 7]. The code was used to obtain a minimum weight laminate arrangement which still satisfied design ultimate load requirements. The static test stabilizer which failed at 109 percent of design ultimate load [7], was used to correlate the analytical procedures. In the present effort, the ASOP program is used to predict the local behavior near the rectangular cutout in the conical shell (see Figure 1, and Section 3).

The PANBUCK II-R code evaluates critical buckling loads for orthotropically layered, rectangular plates and honeycomb sandwich panels. The effects of normal shear stiffness and membrane-bending coupling terms are included. In addition to overall buckling, the program determines local instability modes of failure such as layer instability, laminate instability, and face wrinkling (including face dimpling, face instability, filament compression fracture, interlaminar shear failure, core shear failure, core separation, and core crushing), for specific composite constructions. Initial laminate waviness is included in the analysis. The analytical predictions have been compared to available test data for boron/epoxy sandwich panels, and other composite plates, [8] with good correlation. For boron/epoxy panels the experimental-analytical correlation is usually within 15%.

The STARS-2 system of codes is a shell of revolution analysis system based upon the procedure of numerically integrating the shell theory equilibrium and compatibility equations [2]. These programs have seen wide application to metallic structures [9, 11], including the laminated and sandwich types of structures found in the shells of the various stages of the SATURN boost vehicle [10]. Experimental correlation for both stress and stability predictions (for non imperfection-sensitive shells) has in general been quite good. For imperfection-sensitivity considerations, experimental correlation factors [12, 13] are applied to the analytical results. The STARS integrated Hooke's Laws are orthotropic with bending-membrane coupling:

$$\begin{pmatrix} N_1 \\ N_2 \\ N_{12} \\ M_1 \\ M_2 \\ M_{12} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} K_{11} & K_{12} & 0 & C_{11} & C_{15} & 0 \\ K_{12} & K_{22} & 0 & C_{15} & C_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & K_{33} & 0 & 0 & C_{16} \\ C_{11} & C_{15} & 0 & D_{11} & D_{12} & 0 \\ C_{15} & C_{22} & 0 & D_{12} & D_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & C_{16} & 0 & 0 & D_{33} \end{bmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} E_1 \\ E_2 \\ E_{12} \\ K_1 \\ K_2 \\ K_{12} \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} N_{T1} \\ N_{T2} \\ 0 \\ M_{T1} \\ M_{T2} \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (1)$$

where the T subscripted terms are thermal load functions. Although bending-twisting crosscoupling terms should be included even for pseudo-orthotropic laminates ($\pm \theta$ ply symmetry), these terms tend to become negligible as the number of plies increases.

To test the applicability of the STARS-2 programs to the analysis of composite shell stability (as well as testing the applicability of the correlation factors of Ref. 12), the results of Ref. 14 were evaluated. Therein sample boron/epoxy and boron/epoxy reinforced titanium cylinders were buckled under axial compression. The correlation obtained for the samples analyzed using STARS-2 is presented in Table I. As can be seen the correlation for these samples, using the experimental factors given in Ref. 12 from tests upon metallic cylinders, is within 10%. Of course these samples are not of sandwich construction, and therefore are not subject to some of the local buckling modes which are possible in the conical shell described in the next section.

3-DESIGN, ANALYSIS, AND TEST OF CONICAL SHELL

3.1 Design

The structure designed, analyzed, and tested in this program is a truncated conical shell, as shown in Figure 1, approximately 64 cm. high and with an included apex half angle of 51 deg. The structural requirements include Mid Bay (MB) support points, 5.08 cm.-diameter MB cutouts and four cutouts at the lower ring, each approximately 12.7 cm. square. Two concentric rings for local attachments are required on the aft side of the cone. An external cylindrical shell is also required for attachment.

The criteria utilized for the design of the composite conical shell are:

- The structure shall have sufficient strength to withstand ultimate load (1.25 times limit load) without failure
- There shall be no excessive deformation of the structure at limit load
- The structure shall maintain its specified stiffness and strength requirements throughout the vehicle service life of 10 years
- The structure shall be capable of sustaining 350°F and maintain structural integrity at that temperature

These structural criteria are satisfied by utilizing the following design philosophy on the advanced-composite structure:

- Ultimate-strength design-allowable data were utilized to satisfy the ultimate-load requirements. These data are based on statistically reduced laminate test data, where available, to provide a MIL-HDBK-5A 'B' basis allowable (90 percent probability of survival with a 95 percent confidence level). In addition, the structure is designed to withstand ultimate load without buckling.
- The limit load and service life requirements are satisfied by use of filament-controlled laminates, the (0, 90, ±45) or (0, ±60) family of laminates. Behavior of laminates is elastic almost to failure; hence, for laminates designed to the ultimate strength criterion, strains and deformations at limit load are elastic. In addition, residual strength tests on specimens previously subjected to fatigue loading

and environmental exposure indicate negligible degradation of both stiffness and strength of filament-controlled properties.

This program has concentrated on a graphite/epoxy conical shell design. During an initial study, two structural concepts (truss and shell) and numerous material options, including graphite/epoxy (both high and intermediate modulus), boron/epoxy, boron/graphite/epoxy, boron/aluminum, aluminum, and titanium, were investigated. It was concluded that for the shell structure essentially equal weight savings, approximately 23 percent as compared to the aluminum structure, could be achieved utilizing either intermediate-modulus graphite/epoxy or boron/epoxy. The intermediate-modulus graphite/epoxy was chosen for this program because of its lower cost. It was also shown that the shell concept leads to a superior structure.

The specific materials chosen for use on this program were Hercules AS/3501 graphite/epoxy, NARMCO's Metlbond 329 epoxy adhesive, and fiberglass-reinforced heat-resistant phenolic honeycomb core. The graphite/epoxy prepreg was chosen to satisfy the high-temperature (350°F) criterion, to maintain the best cost advantage over other advanced-composite designs, and to utilize existing data for mechanical properties and design allowables. The adhesive, MB 329, was also chosen to satisfy the high-temperature criterion and to best utilize existing data. The core material was chosen to preclude a galvanic-corrosion problem reported in Ref. 15.

Having chosen the basic materials, and eliminated the truss concept in favor of the shell, several design options were still available. Initial design studies included stiffened-shell and honeycomb sandwich-shell concepts for the conical shell. The stiffened-shell concepts consisted of a plain graphite/epoxy laminate cone, stiffened by either constant-hat-section individual stiffeners or a corrugated sheet having tapered-hat-section stiffeners. A major problem for these configurations was that the stiffeners and the two circumferential rings for local attachments were both fitted to the underside of the cone. Because the direction of the primary cone load was axial, continuous stiffeners were desired; therefore, two alternative ring concepts were investigated.

Initially, a ring with cutouts at each stiffener location was evaluated. An open section was chosen for the rings to provide access for the initial installation of hardware for the local attachments, and for subsequent replacement should any hardware be damaged during service. The cutouts complicated the manufacture of the rings and the interrupted ring structure was of limited effectiveness. An alternate ring configuration was studied where the two circumferential rings were seated on top of the stiffeners. This gave the rings a shallower continuous section. The loads from the ring are transferred to the stiffeners by metal clips.

Although the shear connection between the ring and the basic cone is now interrupted, this configuration was thought to be more efficient for numerous closely spaced stiffeners. The former configuration of rings with webs connected to the basic cone between stiffeners is more attractive for configurations with larger stiffener spacings.

Tradeoff studies were made of the two stiffener designs, and the corrugated sheet proved to be the lighter. The tradeoff study also included variations in the shell laminate. Both the quasi-isotropic laminate and an arbitrary laminate which would require fabrication of pie-shaped pieces were investigated. The arbitrary laminate yields a weight saving, but has increased fabrication costs. In the lightest configuration which has the highest number of stiffeners, a minimum laminate was used and the cone could, therefore, be fabricated either way for equal weight.

A serious problem associated with the stiffened-shell concept was overall stability. The theoretical collapse, as given by the STARS-2 analysis, is at a load factor of approximately 1.40 on ultimate load. This is considerably lower than the required 2.50 factor (considering the correlation factors of Ref. 13), and indicates that the rings are not enforcing nodes as assumed for preliminary sizing. As a result of the collapse problem, and an additional problem in local-load introduction, a honeycomb sandwich cone was investigated. A structure with a load factor of 2.50 on ultimate load for overall collapse and which was configured within the design constraints was arrived at, and is shown in Figure 2. Features of this concept include:

- Titanium rings at each end of the cone, which eliminate the need for the composite to be fabricated around any corners, keeping this design within existing technology. These rings include a graphite/epoxy overwrap which provides additional strength and stiffness at a weight saving. The rings are bonded to both face sheets of the sandwich cone
- A graphite/epoxy outer cylinder similar to that of the stiffened design
- An upper titanium attachment ring to accommodate the threaded pickups for the MB attachments
- Aluminum cups are provided at the local load introduction points. As shown, they will be designed for the specified loads at approximately 7.6 cm. spacings; any higher local load would require the insertion of a larger individually designed fitting.

A laminate study was performed to determine the optimum face sheet laminates for the overall collapse criteria. The laminates and resulting load factors are shown in Table II. Both uniform

laminated face sheets, and face sheets with buildups in a central band around the cone were investigated. All laminates are of equal weight; therefore, the highest load factor relates to the optimum laminate. From the results shown, the eight-ply quasi-isotropic uniform face sheets give essentially the best load factor attainable. This laminate simplifies fabrication because it eliminates the need for cutting pie-shaped tapes.

A preliminary weight summary for both concepts indicates cone weight totals of 54.4 kg. and 57.6 kg. for the honeycomb sandwich and stiffened cones, respectively. These weights were derived from preliminary designs.

Although the sandwich cone weight is comparable to that of the stiffened cone, it must be realized that the stiffened cone does not satisfy the overall collapse requirements. Because these weights are approximately equal and the stiffened cone is inadequate, it is anticipated that the honeycomb sandwich design will effect a weight saving over a satisfactory stiffened design. In addition, the stiffened-cone concept results in a higher cost structure. This results from the complexity and number of stiffeners as compared with the simplicity of making another conical shell for a honeycomb sandwich cone. The cost of the honeycomb sandwich concept was kept to a minimum by tooling the faying surfaces of the face sheets and using a constant-thickness core. The honeycomb core was used in its "as-received" thickness. Because of these weight and cost savings, plus elimination of the local load introduction problem associated with the stiffened cone, the honeycomb sandwich design was chosen.

3.2 Analysis

The internal load distribution for the conical shell was determined using the STARS-2S computer program [2]. The shell model utilized for the static analysis of the base frame is shown in Figure 3. The idealization is made up of a system of 28 nodes, 28 members, 10 rings, and 6 rigid links. All members are plate-shell bending segments with sandwich-wall segments being used for the basic shell. The ring elements represent local areas not accounted for in the plate or shell idealization. The rigid links are used to represent fasteners for single-fastener joints or to couple elements at the ends of the conical shell.

The idealization includes a significant refinement in the areas of the titanium rings to represent the double flanges which are bonded to the sandwich face sheets and the double-fastener bolted joint at the lower ring. These refinements were incorporated to determine load distributions where redundant load paths occurred. The fasteners in this double row are represented by segments matching the stiffness of the fasteners. The lower end of the outer cylinder is supported by a cylindrical segment and a second cylindrical segment is included at the upper end of the

shell to represent the flexibilities of the adjacent structure.

A schematic of the external applied loads is given in Figure 4. The two load conditions found to be critical for the design are given by having all of the loads in the positive or negative sense simultaneously, and are designated the compression and tension condition, respectively. The distributed axial, bending, and shear loads were input to the STARS-2S analysis as line loads of the lower-order Fourier harmonics. Concentrated point loads on the MB ring were approximated by higher-order harmonics. The local loads were assumed to be applied at the inner shell surface; therefore, the loads applied at the mid-plane of the shell included a vertical component and moment due to the offset.

Continuous analyses were used to determine the peak loading at the edge of the MB and aluminum cup cutouts. These cutouts were modeled as circular holes in infinite and finite plates for the MB and aluminum cup cutouts, respectively. For the circular hole in the infinite plate, a concentration factor of 3.39 was used as determined from the analysis of Ref. 16. Finite-plate corrections of Ref. 17 were applied for the analysis of the aluminum cup cutouts; a concentration factor of 2.60 was calculated.

A finite-element analysis of the rectangular cutout was performed using membrane panels, plate bending elements, and beam elements in the ASOP program [3]. A 32-deg segment of the cone, Figure 5, from $Z = -10.24$ cm. (below the lower corner ring) to $Z = 32.77$ cm. (above the upper mid-ring) was idealized with one boundary through the cutout centerline taken as a plane of symmetry. Tangential displacement constraint was simulated at the 32-deg plane. Symmetrical loads from the STARS-2S analysis were applied to the upper boundary. Symmetrical external loads were applied to the mid-rings. At the lower boundary, axial displacements were constrained and rotation was permitted only about the axial (Z) direction.

Preliminary analysis did not include the upper portion of the graphite/epoxy cylinder shown in Figure 5 and neglected the flexural stiffness of the lower corner ring. Both were included in the final analysis.

Material properties and loads for 350°F were used in preliminary and final analyses. The design condition was subsequently changed to 250°F, but the estimated weight saving for the cutout region, approximately 0.1 kg., did not justify further analysis and design effort. A requirement for small radii in the cutout lower corners was also subsequently relaxed, but this change was not incorporated in the finite element analysis.

The overall buckling analysis of the cone structure was performed using the STARS-2B computer program [2]. The structural idealization utilized for the stability analysis was similar to that for the static analysis, Figure 3, except that the additional refinement at the ends of the conical shell was eliminated. The cone-cylinder junctions were idealized as a three-element junction at one node; this reduced the idealization to 16 nodes and 16 segments.

In the shell theory used for the stability analysis, only axisymmetric loading is considered in a rigorous fashion. Thus, unsymmetric loads are considered by taking the worst-meridian approach, i.e., assuming the worst-meridian stress state to be axisymmetric. In all cases, the structure is idealized as being axisymmetric by smearing all stringers and weakening effects due to cutouts, as required. The actual stability analysis is carried out using an iteration approach where the transcendental eigenvalue problem is solved by a successive series of linear approximations [2]. If the loading is truly axisymmetric, predeformation is considered. In the worst-meridian approach, the inclusion of predeformation is not recommended and was not used. The analysis in all cases is based on an eigenvalue approach rather than a nonlinear equilibrium collapse.

The conical shell structure was analyzed under the application of an axisymmetric load representative of the actual unsymmetric loading configuration. Buckling in a substantial number of Fourier harmonics was investigated to find the critical state; the results are presented in Figure 6. While the points on the initial curve at the lower harmonics indicate critical overall buckling may occur in the 3rd or 4th harmonic, a number of rather local meridional buckling modes were uncovered in the higher harmonics. The load multiplier values plotted are theoretical predictions. In addition, reductions are applied to the load factors in the critical regions using experimental correlation factors [12, 13] of 0.41 and 0.58 in the low and high harmonic regions, respectively. In the high harmonics, the local modes appear to involve mainly the inner cylinder and the adjacent reinforcement area comprised of a cylinder and annular plate. (The mode shape for the second-lowest critical load in this harmonic region involves only the outer cylinder.) The experimental correlation factor for these modes is, therefore, governed mainly by the cylinder dimensions and appears to be approximately 0.58 [12].

To determine the applicable correlation factor for the lower harmonics, the recommendations of Ref. 13 for the stability of truncated cones were utilized. Correlation factors of 0.33 and 0.75 are presented for axial compression and external pressure, respectively. In the conical base frame, internal axial loads N_y and hoop loads N_θ exist for the given loading conditions. These internal loads relate to the axial compression and external pressure conditions, respectively. The following interaction equation with an arbitrary power was assumed:

$$\left(\frac{N_{\phi}}{\bar{N}_{\phi}}\right)^n + \left(\frac{N_{\theta}}{\bar{N}_{\theta}}\right)^n = \left(\frac{1}{\text{Load Factor}}\right)^n \quad (2)$$

The applicable power, n , was determined by utilizing the STARS-2B analysis of the conical base frame under the separate pre-stress states: (1) N_{ϕ} only, (2) N_{θ} only, and (3) N_{ϕ} and N_{θ} . With the substitution of the buckling loads for these cases into the interaction equation, the value of n was calculated to be 1.7. Using this value and the recommended knockdown factors gives:

$$\left(\frac{N_{\phi}}{0.33 \bar{N}_{\phi}}\right)^{1.7} + \left(\frac{N_{\theta}}{0.75 \bar{N}_{\theta}}\right)^{1.7} = \left(\frac{1}{\gamma_{\text{eff}} \text{ Load Factor}}\right)^{1.7} \quad (3)$$

and the effective knockdown factor for the combined condition, γ_{eff} , is calculated to be 0.41. Using this value in addition to the higher harmonic analysis, the required theoretical load factors for the lower and higher harmonics modes are 2.44 and 1.72, respectively. For the test component, the anticipated stability failure is at an overall load factor of 1.3.

Some of the critical points at the higher harmonics were obtained with some difficulty in convergence. It generally appeared that the influence of the second-lowest root was much stronger than that of the first on the convergence scheme. It is felt that this may be caused by the fact that for the local buckling modes found, the structural-model idealization may be rather coarse, in both integration points and segments, causing convergence difficulties to arise. Thus, a finer model should be made, either overall or in the local areas, to obtain further checks on the analytical results. It was decided, however, that the requirements for this refined analysis would be clarified by the correlation of the present results with the experimental investigation. This delay was further justified by the fact that the adjusted (correlation factors) results do not seem to uncover a critical overall buckling mode in the basic cone structure.

The predicted controlling factors in the design of the base frame were the following. The basic laminate on each face sheet was governed by shell-buckling considerations; therefore, areas of high margins were available on a strength basis. The laminate buildups at the attachment of the MB ring, Station 66.04, were sized by bearing considerations for the upper laminate and local bending considerations from the reverse tension loading for the lower laminate. Upper laminate buildups at the cups, Station 78.0 and 95.8, were sized by the net section strengths. For these calculations, the aluminum cup flanges were assumed to offer no reinforcement around the holes except for encapsulation of the graphite/epoxy. The face sheet bonds were generally of a minimum

overlap and showed ample margins. The titanium rings were sized by a combination of meridional bending and circumferential stresses, as was the graphite/epoxy outer cylinder. One area which showed significant margins is the buildup area around the larger rectangular cutouts. This area was originally designed using preliminary internal load distributions, which showed significantly greater peaking than at present. The strain-gage data obtained during the component test was to be used to verify the ASOP analysis around the cutout.

3.3 Testing

The specimen, attached around its base on a structural steel fixture cylinder, was tested to the design loads increased by appropriate factors to account for room temperature testing. A survey of the analytically predicted margins of safety on the graphite/epoxy base frame indicates that the critical margins for compression loading are 0.07 and 0.17 at 250°F and room temperature, respectively. For tension loading, the critical margins are 0.12 and 0.24. Therefore, the ratio of room temperature to 250°F strength is 1.10 and 1.11 for compression and tension, respectively. For testing the shell, the design loads were increased by these appropriate factors and designated room temperature "test" loads. A change in the local load requirements, N_1 and N_2 , was made. The revised loads were distributed between the two attachment rings in the same proportion as the original loads.

The loading sequence for the test component was:

- Limit load in the tension condition
- Limit load in the compression condition
- Ultimate load in the compression condition with loading continued to failure.

The test fixture, was designed to apply and react the test load in a manner representative of an actual vehicle installation. A total of 180 strain-gage circuits, and six electronic deflection transducers were incorporated on the specimen.

After installing the specimen in the test fixture and making load and instrumentation connections for the tension limit load condition, the following test procedure was employed:

- Ran a functional test to 40 percent of limit load in 10 percent increments. Recorded all load, strain, and deflection data at each increment, and monitored the specimen acoustic emission as the loads were applied.

- Ran tension condition to 100 percent of limit load and then unloaded, recording the required data
- Changed the horizontal load equipment to the compression position. Attached the six hydraulic jacks to the whiffle-tree system inside the steel fixture cylinder
- Ran a functional test to 40 percent of ultimate load in the compression condition
- Ran the compression condition to limit load (80 percent of test ultimate load) and then unloaded. Repeated to limit load, then increased in 5 percent increments to test ultimate and then to failure

In this configuration the lower ring of the conical shell specimen collapsed ± 120 deg around the 0-deg position as shown in Figure 7, at 110 percent of the test ultimate load. Because this failure was influenced by the attachment to the test fixture, the failed area was repaired and the specimen re-tested to give the desired data relative to shell failure. The repair consisted of reinforcement with steel doubler plates. For repair of the outer cylinder of the specimen, all of the two- and three-gage rosettes on the ring obstructing the doubler plates were removed. Upon completion of the repair, the compression condition was re-tested using a similar test procedure, and failure occurred at 105 percent of test ultimate load.

3.4 Analytical - Experimental Correlation

Testing of the component demonstrated ultimate-load capability of the graphite/epoxy conical shell. The initial failure occurred at 110 percent of test ultimate load at the attachment to the lower test fixture. Previous testing to limit-load conditions indicated linear load-strain behavior up to limit load and no permanent set. Gages in the upper portions of the shell indicated non-linear behavior above limit load. This behavior, as shown in Figure 8 seems to indicate the proximity of the structure to its critical buckling load. Such strain data behavior is typical at the proximity of stability failures of structures.

The analytical critical buckling load was 1.3 times design ultimate load, as determined by the STARS-2B shell analysis, which neglects the normal shear flexibility of the shell. Using an equivalent flat panel and the PANBUCK II-R computer program [5], an approximation of the reduction due to shear flexibility was determined. Applying this reduction to the overall collapse load of the shell gives an anticipated stability failure at 0.95 design ultimate load. This, coupled with the non-linear increase in shell bending, evidenced by the strain-gage data, indicates that the failure was initiated by an overall collapse stability mode and that

this stability mode was influenced by the low shear stiffness of the honeycomb core.

Subsequent re-testing indicated no further increased load capability, although the behavior in the upper portion of the shell was demonstrated to be repeatable. During this re-test, failure occurred at 105 percent of test ultimate load in the upper portion of the shell, below the aluminum MB ring. Figure 9 is a photograph of a section of the sandwich-shell failure area. The failure, initiated by an overall collapse, appears to have resulted in a compression failure of the outer face sheet. Using maximum strain data as recorded during test, the outer face sheet at gage location -9 experienced a combined stress state, equivalent to 103 percent of the design-allowable stress level, or 85 percent of predicted average failure stress. This correlation is quite reasonable because the gage location is not necessarily at the location of the peak shell bending.

Deflections measured during test indicated linear load-deflection behavior to test ultimate load, with a total vertical deflection of an MB support point of 0.653 cm. at test ultimate load.

A summary of the measured strains and comparison to predicted values is given in Table III. The gages for which data are given include some at the maximum loaded portion of the shell, those around a latitudinal cut below the MB ring, those in the outer cylinder, and those giving peak strains recorded at the cutouts. Correlation between test and predicted values is satisfactory considering that the local test loads were reduced and the predicted values of strain do not include this load reduction.

Strain data from the top of the shell and around the latitudinal cut indicate essentially identical membrane loading in this area, with an increased shell bending when compared with analytical data. This increased bending leads to increases in the face sheet axial strains of 20 percent at the top of the shell and from 23 to 35 percent along the latitudinal cut which is at the failure location. In the upper portion of the shell, hoop strains agree more closely with predicted values, with most of the differences also attributable to the increased bending. At the cutouts, strain-gage data indicate readings of 76 and 74 percent of predicted values at the rectangular and MB cutouts, respectively. These lower values are due partially to the reduction in loading and partially to the averaging behavior of the gages. Surveying the outer cylinder strain-gage data in the area of peak loading indicates significantly less hoop strain and axial wall bending than predicted. This is, at least in part, due to the load reductions.

4 - CONCLUSIONS

The conclusions that can be drawn from this effort are basically as follows:

- The full-scale composite conical shell, which is significantly lighter than its metallic counterpart, was tested successfully to 110% of ultimate load. Thus the applicability of advanced composite shallow-cone structures, and the static strength structural integrity of this selected design, were demonstrated.
- Existing advanced composites technology was sufficient for the design, analysis, tooling, and fabrication phases of this effort.
- The automated analytical tools, when properly combined, allowed for satisfactory experimental-theoretical correlation. Due to the changing load requirements, the analytic predictions did not fully mirror the test conditions. Although a refinement of the analysis would have been desirable, this was not done since this effort was one of a group, and the others showed equally good analytical-experimental correlations to completely justify the use of these types of computer programs.
- The overall collapse predictions were surprisingly accurate in spite of the approximations involved in the theory such as: a) worst meridian approach to the unsymmetric stability problem; b) the use of experimental correlation factors from metallic experimental data; c) a linear eigenvalue analysis. Actually the most significant effect found omitted in the STARS analysis was the shear deformation effects for this type of composite face-sheet sandwich construction. The PANBUCK II-R approximation of this effect reduced the predicted collapse load to 73% of the STARS prediction. Had this effect been included in the STARS coded shell theory the load redistribution in the shell, and thus the collapse condition, could have been predicted even more accurately.

5 - REFERENCES

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Table I. Experimental-Analytical Comparisons: Cylinder Buckling

Specimen [15]	(\bar{N}_x) exp. kN/m	(\bar{N}_x) calc. kN/m	mode	Correlation factor used in calculation [13]
100-11a (No. 2) (Boron/epoxy)	2455	2530	2	.77
100-13 (Boron/epoxy)	1753	1601	2	.75
101-13a (Boron/epoxy reinf. titanium)	1459	1390	2	.72

Table II. Sandwich Cone Laminate Orientation Study

Laminate	Percent Laminate Orientation			Load Factor
	0°	90°	± 45°	
[0/90/±45] _s	25	25	50	2.51
[0 ₂ /90/±45] _s	50	25	25	2.12
[0/90 ₂ /±45] _s	25	50	25	2.37
[0 ₃ /90 ₃ /±45] _T	37.5	37.5	25	2.32
[0 ₃ /90/±45 ₂] _T	37.5	12.5	50	2.31
[(0/±60)/±45] _s	18.8*	18.8*	62.5*	2.54
[(0/±60)] _s + [±45 ₂]**				2.51
[(0/±60)] _s + [0/90] _s **				2.36
[(0/±60)] _s + [0/90/±45] _T **				2.48

*Equivalent percentages
 **Additional plies in central region

Table III. Typical Strain-Gage Data at Test Ultimate Load ($\mu\text{m/m}$)

Gage No.	Hoop Gage (-1)			Shear Gage (-2)			Meridional Gage (-3)		
	Pred	Test 2	Test 2A	Pred	Test 2	Test 2A	Pred	Test 2	Test 2A
-43	-2100	-1432	-1388	---	---	---	-2354	-2839	-2846
-44	-1265	-1470	-1416	---	---	---	-1342	-680	-712
-41	-1980	-1532	-1448	---	---	---	-3708	-4577	-4661
-42	-748	-992	-972	---	---	---	-2761	-1229	-1197
-9	-1530	-1203	-1086	-2692	-2577	-2514	-3470	-4551	-4772
-10	-1530	-1647	-1653	-2317	-740	-748	-2720	-1293	-1273
-15	-2020	-1713	-1673	-2970	-2660	-2707	-3490	-4583	-4647
-16	-800	-668	-622	-1841	-747	-789	-2453	-781	-755
-17	-2090	-1696	-1685	-2833	-2457	-2469	-2959	-3900	-3910
-18	-935	-846	-790	-1639	-248	-248	-1727	-140	-155
-27	-2189	-1631	-1586	-2205	-2191	-2146	-2222	-2990	-3015
-28	-1111	-1080	-1033	-896	-143	-105	-681	-902	-877
-31	-2090	-1670	-1617	-2216	-2923	-2941	-2959	-3770	-3813
-32	-935	-876	-816	-1023	-727	-746	-1727	-32	-86
-7	-418	-344	-501	-2100	-1590	-1343	-3780	-2943	-2780
-8	-198	-506	-616	-1559	-929	-1005	-2920	-2507	-2743
-5	1595	1199	928	-1172	-390	-287	-3940	-2386	-1832
-6	2390	1324	937	-545	-384	-893	-3480	-1993	-2541
-49	3278	1431	---	---	---	---	1067	1084	---
-50	3278	2321	---	---	---	---	-6127	-2366	---
-51	3278	2230	---	---	---	---	1067	1034	---
-52	3278	1915	---	---	---	---	-6127	2779	---
-53	3267	1880	---	---	---	---	1067	1124	---
-54	3267	2323	---	---	---	---	-6105	-2950	---
-71	---	---	---	---	---	---	-4730	-3135	-2387
-72	---	---	---	---	---	---	-3410	-3298	-3812
-73	---	---	---	---	---	---	-2640	-2300	-1445
-74	---	---	---	---	---	---	-3200	-3598	-3694
-69	-176	1214	1129	---	---	---	---	---	---
-70	527	1829	1555	---	---	---	---	---	---
-55	4960	3443	2391	---	---	---	---	---	---
-56	-1650	3970	2363	---	---	---	---	---	---
-23	---	---	---	---	---	---	-4170	-3073	-2920
-24	---	---	---	---	---	---	-3542	-2887	-3149
-25	-890	-290	-156	---	---	---	---	---	---
-26	-890	-290	-156	---	---	---	---	---	---

Fig. 1 General Structural Arrangement

Fig. 3 Structural Idealization—STARS-2S Static Analysis

- 1.25 FACTOR OF SAFETY TO ULTIMATE
- BENDING MOMENT APPLIED AS AXIAL LOAD WITH COSINE DISTRIBUTION
- DESIGN TO WORST-ON-WORST LOAD COMBINATION

Fig. 4 Conical Base Frame Loads

Fig. 5 Idealization of Cone Segment at Rectangular Cutout

Fig. 6 Theoretical Stability Data

Fig. 7 Outer Cylinder Failure, External View

Fig. 8 Typical Non-Linear Axial-Strain Behavior

Fig. 9 Shell Section at Failure Location